

Editorial

The *EVERGREEN* editorial team has been overloaded with several tasks since the departure of our Secretariat, Ms Mieko INOUE. The immediate struggle is in the production of the accepted papers. Running an academic journal is not a simple task. We editors are rather familiar with the handling process, which itself needs skills such as academic judgement and spotting scientific insights. Of course, one of our most important abilities is setting the direction of the journal. However, the production process is a different beast. It requires mastering multiple skills, such as preparing proofs, table of contents, uploading to the journal site, getting the DOIs, etc. Since inception, our secretariat team, including Ms INOUE and the so-called webmaster, had taken care of the smooth production of papers in *EVERGREEN*. Ms INOUE has moved on. And *EVERGREEN* moves forward, with or without adequate support. In any case, how can we call a person who can and is doing all these tasks? Shall we call it AI? Definitely not.

In today's climate, where resilience seems in short supply, it is always a good idea to look at the positive side. Thus, it is often said that having a "postitude" - the short form of "positive attitude" - is crucial to staying healthy, especially mentally. In that sense, there are several positive things happening in *EVERGREEN*, even without our capable Ms. INOUE. The first milestone is the successful publication of *EVERGREEN* Vol. 12, Issue 02. It is encouraging that the journal website has become more modern, shall we say, more professional? We can now see the citation and download counts of the published papers (article metrics) as well as modern features such as sharing tools, export citation tools and an embedded PDF. Most notably, we now have an additional repository for the publishers on Zenodo.

Not everything is rosy though. The first casualty is the handling efficiency. Authors now have to wait longer for the editorial progress of their papers. There may be a couple of reasons. Perhaps the editorial team is diverting time to the production process that was previously handled by support staff. On the other hand, we are facing significant difficulties in finding qualified reviewers. People these days are busy. Many researchers are working extremely hard to get their research papers published, while they may not find time for review. We meant professional and excellent reviews. Of course, we can often find productive reviewers on their academic profiles. It is rather coincidence that several profiles with thousands of review credits turn out to have a huge number of citations of their papers. In some cases, the numbers are incredible. Unbelievably incredible! Of course, *EVERGREEN* is not in that league and tries to stay away from supernatural things. What makes matters worse is the emergence of countless journals these days.

The editorial team is very glad to be able to publish *EVERGREEN* Vol. 12 Issue 03. In this edition, we have several papers that have been rigorously reviewed and judiciously handled. Currently, we do not have the capacity to publish any special issues because of the labour shortage, not to be confused with the popular headline in the developed world countries like Korea, Japan or the European Union, but in *EVERGREEN*.

We would like to express our gratitude to *EVERGREEN* reviewers, who are professional, ethical, and scientific-oriented, yet not very supernatural. We do believe that academic journals can be ranked with the quality of the reviewers. In such a case, *EVERGREEN* should rank pretty high thanks to your trusted reviewers. We would like to record our appreciation of our authors. *EVERGREEN* authors have been very resilient. We are very grateful to our *EVERGREEN* community for being patient with us. The editorial team and management completely understand the current situation. Tremendous efforts have been made to resolve the issues. However, sometimes things are more difficult than they look. Nevertheless, we spare no effort to improve the situation. As we stated in our earlier editorials, this is perhaps a good chance to raise the standard of *EVERGREEN*. Since our hands are tied, we are forced to prioritise the best papers. We will naturally accept fewer papers. Let's look towards a brighter future.

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